

Research

Traffic Emissions from Urban Road Intersections on the Surroundings - A Case Study of Intersection in Shijiazhuang, China

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Abstract: With the rapid advancement of industrialization and urbanization in China, the number of urban motor vehicles has increased rapidly, and the pollution problem of motor vehicle emissions has become increasingly prominent. Therefore, it is necessary to further study the pollutant emission patterns of urban transportation to provide a scientific basis for the solution of pollutant exposure problems among urban residents. Based on the actual investigated traffic data of Shijiazhuang city, the authors combined the VISSIM-MOVES-CALPUFF model to establish the traffic emission inventory of complex intersections in Shijiazhuang city and studied the dynamic diffusion characteristics of the emission in a road section in Shijiazhuang city, on the basis of which a model for calculating the ambient traffic capacity (CET) was established. The results show that (1) the diffusion range of CO and NO_x is larger than that of other pollutants, and the diffusion process is significantly affected by wind direction and wind speed; (2) during the peak traffic period, the concentration of environmental indicators in the road area is much higher than that of the surrounding living environment, whereas the opposite is true for the daily average concentration index. The results of this paper will be of great theoretical and practical significance for enriching the study of pollutant exposure among urban residents, optimizing the road traffic environment, and traffic control at road intersections.

Keywords: Intersections, traffic emissions, MOVES model, CALPUFF model, Capacity of Environment Traffic (CET)

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Introduction

Numerous studies have shown that road transport is a significant source of air pollution in most urban areas worldwide (Rosenlund et al. 2008; Su et al. 2009; Uherek et al. 2010; Lozhkina and Lozhkin 2015; Réquia et al. 2015). With the rapid development of China's transportation industry and the increase in motor vehicle ownership, GHG emissions from transportation have become an important driver of total national GHG emissions (Li et al. 2020). Many studies have

reported that traffic emission exposure is associated with cardiovascular disease (Requia et al. 2016), asthma (Lemke et al. 2014), hypertension (Weichenthal et al. 2014), diabetes (Nicole 2015), and neurological disorders (Genc et al. 2012), among many other diseases. At urban traffic intersections, changes in driving patterns (idle, acceleration, deceleration, and cruise modes) often produce uncertain emissions. In addition, pedestrian movement and wind effects further contribute to the random dispersion of pollutants (He et al. 2009). Although the emergence of advanced transportation technologies (electric vehicles, hydrogen-fueled vehicles, etc.) can alleviate the pressure on transportation emissions, these technologies cannot produce appreciable emission reductions in the short term (Nichols et al. 2015; Amirgholy et al. 2017; Miralinaghi et al. 2017). Therefore, it is necessary to study the traffic emission patterns at urban road intersections to provide a theoretical basis for safeguarding the health of urban residents and traffic control.

CALPUFF (California Puff Model) is considered to be one of the most powerful environmental modeling programs. It has been used by many researchers to study and simulate pollutant concentrations, as well as to model the effects of meteorological and geophysical conditions on the dispersion of target pollutants (Abdul-Wahab et al. 2011; Charabi et al. 2018; Murena et al. 2018; Fuentes García et al. 2022). There are also many studies on the application of the CALPUFF model in China. Song et al. (2006) conducted a study using CALPUFF with the aim of identifying the main sources of emissions that contribute to high concentrations of particulate matter in Beijing winter. Wu et al. (2017) attempted to develop an effective restoration plan to reduce the concentrations of pollutants such as PM₁₀, SO₂, and NO_x in the air of Benxi City by using the results of CALPUFF. Hao and Xie (2018) used CALPUFF for simulation to predict SO₂ and NO₂ concentrations to determine the best location for air quality monitoring stations in Shijiazhuang City and so on. Therefore, this paper adopts the CALPUFF model as one of the methods to study the pollutant emissions at the intersection.

Many studies have used different methods such as emission inventories, geographic information systems (GIS), dispersion models, and exposure indicators to investigate spatial patterns of traffic emissions and human exposure (Wallace et al. 2012; Guttikunda and Calori 2013; Rodriguez et al. 2013; Oakes et al. 2014). Quantification of motor vehicle emissions is essential to estimate their impact on local air quality and traffic-related exposures. Such quantification requires the collection of travel activity data over space and time and the development of emission inventories (Shah et al. 2006; Bellasio et al. 2007; Kassomenos et al. 2009). Emission inventories are usually developed based on emission models; for example, vehicle emission inventories are estimated by calculating the exhaust and evaporation rates of greenhouse gases and pollutants (e.g., HC, CO, NO_x, PM, SO₂, NH₃) produced by specific vehicle types and fuels using models such as IVE (International Vehicle Emissions), MOVES (Motor Vehicle Emission Simulator), and COPERT (Computer Program for Estimating Road Transport Emissions) (Ergun et al. 2014; Jiang et al. 2020). Although MOVES consists of software based on U.S. fuel types and standards, its local adaptation can be used for pollutant dispersion and emission inventory creation in China (Li et al. 2020; Tong et al. 2020).

In this paper, the authors applied VISSIM (a microscopic traffic simulation software) to assist MOVES and the CALPUFF model to jointly study motor vehicle pollutant emissions at Shijiazhuang intersections. Firstly, the authors used the VISSIM-MOVES model to establish the traffic emission inventory of typical intersections and urban road sections in Shijiazhuang. Secondly, the authors developed an environmental allowable traffic volume calculation model by referring to the traffic emission inventory and combining the MOVES emission factor and CALPUFF dilution factor to calculate the environmental allowable traffic volume of the intersection and road section. Finally, the authors evaluate whether the actual traffic volume at the intersection exceeds the environmental standard traffic limit and provide recommendations for traffic control and healthy travel for residents. The framework of this paper is shown in Figure 1.

Fig. 1: Framework of the paper

Case location

The research area of this paper is located at the intersection of Tiyu Street and Heping Road in Chang'an District, Shijiazhuang City, Hebei Province, China (as shown in Figure 2). The intersection is an important node of the road network in Chang'an District, and the traffic flow is dense. During the study period, most of the surrounding areas of the intersection were residential areas and old workshops with shutdown control. The emission of traffic sources became the primary source of pollution in the area. Therefore, the study area has representative research on the emission of pollutants at intersections. Based on the actual situation, it is planned to select the intersection of Shijiazhuang Tiyu Street and He Ping Road as the research point source object.

(a) Geographical location of Shijiazhuang

(b) Geographic location of the study area

(c) Street view of the intersection

(d) Intersection traffic organization of the intersection

Fig. 2: Traffic situation in the study area

As shown in Figure 2(c, d), there is a viaduct built above the intersection section and on the peace road, and the viaduct does not intersect with Tiyu Street. Combined with the actual situation and under comprehensive consideration, the authors chose the intersection as the research point and source object and investigated the relevant data. The traffic organization structure at this intersection is shown in Figure 2(d).

Research Methodology

Model introduction:

The MOVES model is a quantitative model of vehicle emissions developed to meet the needs of traffic environmental impact analysis and evaluation. Many researchers have used it to conduct emission inventory studies, and its multi-scale and high simulation accuracy are suitable for the simulation of intersection emissions (Li et al. 2020; Zhang et al. 2020; Sun et al. 2021). CALPUFF (California Puff Model) can simulate the transport, transformation, and removal processes of pollutants in the atmospheric environment over time and space. Therefore, the authors mainly used the MOVES model and the CALPUFF model (California Puff Model) to conduct the experiments and used VISSIM traffic simulation software (a simulation modeling tool based on time interval and driving behavior which can analyze the operation of urban traffic and public transportation under various traffic conditions such as lane settings, traffic composition, traffic signals, etc.) to assist in studying the intersection pollutant dispersion study.

Data acquisition:

(1) Road network traffic flow data

The authors collected traffic volume on weekdays and weekends in October 2022 by combining manual counting with video recording. The time span of each survey was 7:00 a.m.-19:00 p.m., and it was divided into seven time periods. Each time period is 1 hour, and the first and third quarters of each time period are taken for manual technology, and the traffic flow of the whole time is obtained by doubling the number. The authors collate the initial survey data and obtain the traffic flow data for the intersection and each road section on the working day, as shown in Appendix A.

(2) Intersection traffic infrastructure data

The traffic parameters that need to be entered in the VISSIM model are: lane profile, lane canalization length, signal information, sidewalk width and width of each green barrier, and the number of each left-turn, straight-turn, and right-turn lane in each entrance direction. The authors obtained data through survey and research as shown in Figure 2(d), Table 1, and Table 2.

Table 1 Traffic organization situation at the intersection of Tiyu Street and Heping Road

Category	Lane data	Eastbound	Westbound	Southbound	Northbound
entrance	Number of lanes	5	6	4	6
	Lane width/m	3.2	3.2	3.2	3.2
	Lane Division Description	2 left turns	4 left turns	1 left turn	1 left turn
		2 straight	1 straight right	2 straight	3 straight lines
		1 right turn	1 right turn	1 straight right	1 straight right 1 right turn
	Non-motorized vehicle lane width/m	4.5	6	4.7	4.7
	Separator width/m	Green Belt 1.5	Green Belt 1.5	Green Belt 1.5	fence 0
Inlet and outlet median width/m		15	12	1.0	1.5
exit	Number of lanes	4	4	5	4
	Lane width/m	3.2	3.2	3.2/4	3.2
	Lane Division Description	a U-turn	4 straight lines	4 straight lines	4 straight lines
		3 straight lines		1 bus only	
	Non-motorized vehicle lane width/m	6	6	6	4.5
Separator width/m	Green Belt 1.5	Green Belt 1.5	Green Belt 1.5	fence 0	

Table 2 Signal periods of the intersection

NO.	Project	Go straight north-south	Turn left north-south	Things go straight	Turn left	Go straight at the south entrance + turn left at the west entrance
1	cycle	180	180	180	180	180
2	Phase duration	68	30	30	29	23
3	green light duration	65	27	27	26	20
4	yellow light duration	3	3	3	3	3
5	red light time	112	150	150	151	157

(3) Geographical data of the study area

Shijiazhuang mainly contains two landforms, the North China Plain and the Taihang Mountains, which account for about half of the total area. Different terrain conditions will have a huge impact on the diffusion of pollutants. In the calculation process of MOVES and CALPUFF models, two kinds of geographic data (terrain elevation data and land use data) need to be input as parameters of model-related influencing conditions. The source of terrain elevation data in this paper is SRTM public free data; the format is *.tif; the resolution is 90m; and the download sites are www.ds.cr.usgs.gov and www.earthexplorer.usgs.gov. The source of land use data in this paper is the open-source free

Asian part of the GLCC (LULC USGS Global) database of the United States Geological Survey (USGS). The GLC2000 China regional land cover data is directly cropped from the global coverage data with an accuracy of 1 km and a data format of *.img.

(4) Meteorological data of the study area

Shijiazhuang has significant seasonal changes and four distinct seasons, which belong to the temperate monsoon climate. Different meteorological conditions will also have a huge impact on the diffusion of pollutants. Therefore, in the calculation process of MOVES and CALPUFF models, there are two kinds of meteorological data (high-altitude meteorological data and surface meteorological data) that need to be input as the parameters of the model-related influencing conditions. According to the calculation needs, different combinations of meteorological data can be selected. Because the simulation range of the study area is small and the meteorological field is relatively uniform in the plain area, according to the calculation needs, the surface and upper air use a combination of measured data. The data published by the University of Wyoming in the United States is more comprehensive than that of the Shijiazhuang weather station, but the data format needs to be converted. The authors recompiled the data according to the Fortran programming language format, with the elevation parameters as the starting point. The conversion between the lunar day and the Gregorian calendar date involved in this process is completed by the code written by the author. The results of data processing are shown in Table 3.

Table 3 Data from weather sounding (station no. 54511)

Atmospheric pressure (hPa)	Ground clearance (m)	dry-bulb temperature (°C)	wind direction (degree)	air velocity (m/s)
1030	55	-6.7	340	75
1000	265	-8.5	345	125
981	413	-9.7	345	125
925	867	-10.7	5	125
874	1301	-11.1	32	80
850	1516	-12.5	45	60
700	2970	-22.3	345	105
598	4110	-28.3	333	160
500	5400	-31.3	320	220
472	5806	-32.7	317	250
400	6950	-40.9	310	325
347	7903	-46.3	305	395
300	8860	-51.7	300	460
273	9460	-51.7	305	490
255	9900	-56.5	300	480
250	10020	-56.3	300	470
200	11440	-55.3	295	405
168	12547	-51.6	295	415
150	13270	-56.3	295	415
111	15185	-54.3	288	390
105	15539	-55.3	286	385
100	15850	-57.3	285	375
95	16179	-58.1	285	365

[Note: Longitude: 116.28E, Latitude: 39.93N, Ground Elevation: 43]

(5) Acquisition of intersection emission inventory

The intersection part belongs to the microemission model. Based on the local measured data of the intersection, the emission inventory of the intersection part is calculated. The authors established a VISSIM simulation road network for typical plane signal intersections in Shijiazhuang. After obtaining the simulated traffic parameters, the vehicle-specific power (VSP) is calculated, and the intersection emission inventory is calculated from the definition of the corresponding VSP interval on the MOVES model. Yu, Z. (2019) used the MOVES model to calculate the emission inventory of the

intersection at Tiyu Street and Heping Road. His research team used the VSP principle to study the simulation calculation of the intersection's inventory and used the VISSIM model and the MOVES model to couple the intersection's vehicle emission inventory calculation. The process and results of its calculation are applicable to the subsequent research in this paper, so the authors directly quote the results of their microscopic intersection emission calculation as shown in Table 4.

Table 4 Pollutant emission list at intersections during each period on weekdays (g·h-1)

Time period	CO	NOx	PM2.5	PM10
07:00~08:00	14 591.544 2	764.640 6	40.680 4	54.551 7
08:00~09:00	13 479.292 7	623.292 9	30.623 7	43.733 8
10:00~11:00	13 390.829 0	927.178 7	43.621 3	53.601 0
12:00~13:00	13 057.081 4	752.952 6	36.990 3	48.426 4
14:00~15:00	13 021.338 5	820.660 8	35.104 3	49.778 7
16:00~17:00	13 802.623 6	765.673 2	37.022 0	48.363 6
18:00~19:00	13 340.415 7	572.438 1	33.628 1	43.511 3

Parameter setting of simulation:

Based on the field survey data, the intersection VISSIM micro simulation model was established within 500 m of the intersection as the center, and the driving behavior parameters were corrected. The 12 lanes in the four directions of the intersection were set to 12 links for simulation calculation. In this study, Wiedeman99, a car following model, was selected. The minimum headway was set at 1 m, the waiting time before vanishing was 100 s, the emergency stop distance was set at 5 m, the lane change distance was set at a fixed value of 200 m, the accessory part of the safe distance was set at 2.75 m, and the multiple part of the safe distance was set at 3.75 m. After the microtraffic simulation, the accuracy error of the checking model should be within 15%.

The data transformation settings to make the MOVES model meet the Chinese regional study are as follows: The geographic information matches the city of Richmond. Meteorological data are locally recorded data; Model, vehicle age, and fuel information using research, national standards, and local statistical yearbook data.

Related parameters of the CALPUFF model simulation were set as follows: The demarcated research area was within the second Ring Road of Shijiazhuang; the southwest corner coordinates were (274.544 km, 4 209.206 km); the grid spacing was 0.25 km, for a total of 1 976 grid points; and the vertical setting of the grid was set to 10 layers. Set the base time zone (EAST 8 zone) and the datum (WGS-84).

Results and discussion

Establishment of emission inventory:

The MOVES model can calculate the total emissions of different categories of pollutants in the simulation area. At the microlevel, the operating cycle distribution parameter is the core parameter of the MOVES model. Vehicle-specific power (VSP) is the power output in kw/t (or W/kg) per ton of mass moved by the engine (including dead weight). The authors established the operating cycle distribution parameters by introducing vehicle-specific power into the MOVES model and matched the speed parameters along with the introduction of VSP, as shown in Table 5, which was assigned to 23 operating state intervals.

Table 5 Motor vehicle operating mode interval

VSP/(kw·t-1)	Instantaneous speed /(km·h-1)		
	1.6~40.2	40.2~80.5	80.5+
30+	Bin16	Bin30	Bin40
24~30		Bin29	Bin39
18~24		Bin28	Bin38
12~18		Bin27	Bin37
9~12	Bin15	Bin25	Bin35
6~9	Bin14	Bin24	

3~6	Bin13	Bin23	Bin33
0~3	Bin12	Bin22	
<0	Bin11	Bin21	
Idle condition (Bin1)			
brake condition (Bin0)			

VSP comprehensively considers the changes in kinetic energy and potential energy of the motor vehicle and works to overcome the rolling resistance and air resistance of the vehicle. After taking the corresponding parameter values, the VSP of a light vehicle and a heavy vehicle can be calculated as follows:

$$VSP_{light} = v \times (1.1a + 0.132) + 0.302 \times 10^{-3} \times v^3 \tag{1}$$

$$VSP_{heavy} = v \times (a + 0.09199) + 0.169 \times 10^{-3} \times v^3 \tag{2}$$

[Notes: a represents the acceleration of the motor vehicle (m/s²); v represents the motor vehicle speed (m/s).]

In the configuration of "Vehicle Record" in VISSIM simulation evaluation, parameters such as "speed", "acceleration", "road section number," "lane number," "model, and vehicle number," are selected to adjust the random seed, and the simulation outputs one-second motor vehicle running data. The speed and acceleration for each vehicle in each road section were screened out, and the distribution ratio of operating conditions of each vehicle in each link was calculated and sorted out. According to the VSP calculation formula for small and large vans, combined with the working condition intervals in Table 5, the proportion of Bin intervals can be calculated for each link level.

Traffic volume is the main factor that directly affects the emission of pollutants at the intersection of each road section. The authors integrated the traffic volume data measured during October 2022 and plotted the emission inventory of each pollutant at the intersection of each road section calculated for each period to compare and analyze the relationship between traffic volume and each pollutant. The hourly emissions of CO, NOX, PM2.5, PM10, and other pollutants at the intersection are shown in Table 4. Table 4 shows that CO is the main pollutant discharged by motor vehicles at the intersection from the perspective of the total emissions at the intersection. The total emission is dozens that of times of other pollutants, followed by NOX, and other pollutants are few. The combined emission inventory and traffic volume are shown in Figure 3.

Fig. 3: Relationship between total traffic volume at the intersection and pollutant emissions

As can be seen from Figure 3: with the passage of time, there is a corresponding positive correlation between the change in traffic volume and the change in pollutant emissions. From the perspective of emissions, the vehicle emission levels from more to less are CO, NOX, HC, PM10, and PM2.5, and the main motor vehicle exhaust pollutant at this intersection

is CO, which may be related to the fact that heavy and medium trucks in Shijiazhuang are not allowed to enter the urban third ring road 24 hours a day (but permits can be applied if necessary). Traffic restriction policy has some relationship. Therefore, it can be concluded from the figure that the amount of motor vehicle pollutants at urban intersections is generally positively correlated with traffic volume. CO emissions are the highest, NOX emissions are the second, and other pollution are less.

Analysis of intersection traffic emission dispersion results:

(1) Dispersion analysis of traffic pollutants at the road level

The authors simulated the dispersion of pollutants at intersections using the CALPUFF model in combination with the emission inventory calculated by the MOVES emission model described above. Data files of the dispersion distribution of pollutant types on weekdays were obtained from the simulations. After interpreting the data files, visual concentration contour maps were plotted using Surfer software. The concentration dispersion of each pollutant type is shown in Figure 4. Different colors in the figure represent different concentration levels, and the contours of each color are the main contours of the concentration contours, and the concentration units shown in the contours are mg/m³.

Fig. 4: Pollutant diffusion at the intersection

The secondary limits of the basic items of ambient air pollutant concentrations according to Chinese national standards (Table 6) are the reference basis for the pollutant emissions in this paper.

According to the secondary limit values of the basic item concentrations of ambient air pollutants in the Chinese national standards (Table 6), it can be seen from the figure that areas with pollutant CO within the baseline concentration range of 10 mg/m³ are considered to have substandard emission concentrations. The pollutant NOx within the concentration range of 0.2mg/m³ is considered to have an unqualified emission concentration. Areas with PM2.5 concentrations within the range of 0.07mg/m³ are considered to have an unqualified emission concentration. Pollutant PM10 within the concentration range of 0.15mg/m³ is considered a substandard emission concentration, and the above areas require attention.

Table 6 Concentration limits of basic items of ambient air pollutants in China

NO.	Pollutant project	Average time	P-CLV	S-CLV	Unit
1	Sulfur dioxide (SO ₂)	Annual	20	60	µg/m ³
		24-hour	50	150	
		1-hour	150	500	
2	Nitrogen dioxide (NO ₂)	Annual	40	40	µg/m ³
		24-hour	80	80	
		1-hour	200	200	
3	carbon monoxide (CO)	24-hour	4	4	mg/m ³
		1-hour	10	10	
4	Particulate matter (PM10)	Annual	40	70	µg/m ³
		24-hour	50	150	
5	Particulate matter (PM2.5)	Annual	15	35	µg/m ³
		24-hour	35	75	

[Notes: P-CLV (Primary concentration limit value), S-CLV (Secondary concentration limit value)]

We can observe from Figure 4 that the center point according to intersection traffic organization happens to be the highest concentration of pollutants in the whole intersection, which means that traffic pollution spreads outward from the center point of the intersection. This is because the center point is the core of the entire intersection traffic organization, and as a conflict point, poor driving conditions such as slow vehicle speeds, multiple acceleration and deceleration and start-stopping, and traffic congestion during peak hours lead to this phenomenon.

In addition, the authors noted a general tendency for the diffusion direction of the pollutants to shift to the southeast due to the effect of wind. Therefore, the center of pollution concentration shifts from the intersection to the southeast, with the smallest diffusion radius in the northwest and a larger diffusion radius in the southeast.

The authors investigated the differences among the various pollutants by discussing the differences in diffusion areas to find the diffusion characteristics of the intersection. The diffusion ranges of various pollutants have been clearly defined in Figure 4, and to show it more clearly, the geographical diffusion ranges of pollutants in Figure 4 are shown quantitatively in Table 7.

Table 7 Classification diffusion range of pollutants at intersection (Unit: m)

Pollutant	East	West	South	North
CO	1 000	500	450	280
NOX	1 700	960	1 000	290
PM2.5	180	80	80	40
PM10	40	40	40	40

As can be seen from Table 6, the dispersion ranges in descending order of area are: NOX (3.4314km²) > CO (1.095 km²) > PM2.5 (0.0312 km²) > PM10 (0.0064 km²); that is, NOX has the largest dispersion range and PM10 has the smallest. The reasons for these results may be related to the emissions of each pollutant and their physical and chemical properties. There is a significant difference in the overall dispersion area of NOX and CO compared to particulate matter (PM), which has smaller emissions and larger molecular diameters. Therefore, NOX and CO are more representative of traffic emissions, both in terms of emissions and dispersion area.

(2) Analysis of exposure to traffic pollutants at the population level

The authors concluded that in order to study the dispersion of traffic pollution in detail, it is necessary to divide the intersections and select control points for the study. The CULPUFF model will output the pollutant concentrations at the control points separately according to the type, providing detailed data for further numerical studies of this study.

The specific division of intersection control points is set up as shown in Figure 5. Control points R1 and R2 are set in the two residential buildings closest to the center of the intersection; one control point R3, R4, R5, and R6 are set in each of the four directions of the intersection sidewalk; control point R7 is set in the center of the intersection; and a total of seven control points are set.

Fig. 5: Schematic diagram of layout of intersection acceptance points

The authors divided the seven control points into two categories according to their geographical distribution. Points R1 and R2 are residential control points, and the concentration values at this point represent the maximum exposure of this population to pollutants at home. The other five control points are travel receivers, whose concentration values represent the exposure of the travel group located on the road. Finally, the daily average concentrations of each pollutant at the intersection were calculated by the model, as shown in Table 8.

Table 8 Average daily concentration at the intersection (Unit: $\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$)

Point	CO	NOX	PM10	PM2.5
R1	31.30	1.98	1.00	0.80
R2	42.20	2.65	1.05	0.84
R3	15.90	0.99	0.78	0.63
R4	16.80	1.04	0.88	0.71
R5	17.70	1.10	1.01	0.81
R6	18.20	1.13	0.84	0.67
R7	17.30	1.07	0.87	0.70

Usually, the average emission concentration of CO is the highest at all control points. CO is 1-2 orders of magnitude higher than the other three pollutants, and the emission concentration levels of the other three pollutants are basically the same, with NOX being higher and PMX being lower.

In order to reflect the trend of concentration changes of various pollutants at each control point in the figure, the authors reduced the highest concentration of CO by a factor of 10 and made a trend graph together with the other three pollutants, as shown in Figure 6.

Fig. 6: Pollutant concentration at each acceptance point

As shown in Figure 6, the concentrations of all pollutants at control points R1 and R2 are higher than those at control points R3, R4, R5, R6, and R7. Among control points R3, R4, R5, R6, and R7, the daily average concentrations at R5 are higher than the other four, which may be related to the wind direction.

Simulation results show that for the daily average concentrations, the population breathes more pollutants at fixed locations off the road than on the road. That is, the exposure to pollution from traffic is not necessarily less than that from road travel during the period when individuals are in fixed places. This may be due to the higher height and denser density of building structures than intersections, which leads to a prolonged accumulation of pollutant gases that cannot dissipate in a short period of time due to the poor degree of ventilation after diffusion into the area.

In addition, the average concentrations during the peak traffic volume (7:00~8:00 a.m. daily during 5 days) are shown in Figure 7 (the data source is the CALPOST component report of the diffusion model), where control points R1~R2 and R3~R7 represent the exposure concentrations in the residential and road environments, respectively.

Fig. 7: Control point concentration during peak traffic flow

Obviously, during the morning peak period, due to the rapid increase in tailpipe emissions caused by the surge of motor vehicles during the peak period, the road pollution generated by a large number of vehicles fails to dissipate in a short period of time, resulting in a road environment where the concentration of various indicators is much greater than that of the residential environment.

(3) The capacity of environment traffic analysis

The authors have explained the intrinsic law of traffic pollutant dispersion under the influence of meteorological and topographical factors from a qualitative perspective. However, it is not enough to analyze traffic emissions only from a qualitative perspective. In the following paper, the authors will calculate the dilution factor, model the environmental tolerance of traffic volume, and conduct a quantitative study of traffic emissions using the CALPUFF model.

In this paper, the authors refer to the Green-Shield theory (Buchanan 1983) and use it as the basis for the construction of this traffic capacity model. The theory is based on the assumption that the traffic volume is linearly related to the rate of speed, so the theory has a certain degree of empirical reliance and insufficient theoretical explanation at the microscopic traffic level. However, it does not affect the subsequent research on the estimation of atmospheric traffic volume in this paper.

1) Construction of the capacity of environment traffic model algorithm

The authors use the MOVES model to calculate the emission factor and the CALPUFF diffusion model to calculate the dilution factor (dispersion factor) and construct an algorithm to calculate the capacity of environment traffic (CET) based on these two factors. The basic equation for the contribution of a single cluster to the concentration at a receptor point, i.e., the concentration at the receptor point, can be expressed from the diffusion model principle of the integrated pyroclastic fume sampling function equation as:

$$C = \frac{Q}{2\pi\sigma_x\sigma_y} \times g \times \exp\left[-\frac{d_a^2}{2\sigma_x^2}\right] \times \exp\left[-\frac{d_c^2}{2\sigma_y^2}\right] \tag{3}$$

$$g = \frac{2}{2\pi\sqrt{z}\sigma_z} \times \sum_{n \rightarrow -\infty}^{\infty} \exp\left[-\frac{H_e + 2nh^2}{2\sigma_y^2}\right] \tag{4}$$

Table 9 Formula symbols indicate the meaning

Symbols	Meaning	Unit
C	the ground pollutant concentration	g/m ³
Q	the pollutant source intensity	g
σ _x	the x-direction (horizontal) diffusion coefficient	m
σ _y	the y-direction (vertical) diffusion coefficient	m
σ _z	the z-direction (vertical) diffusion coefficient	m
d _a	the distance from the center of the plume in the x-direction to the receptor point	m
d _c	the distance from the center of the plume in the y-direction to the receptor point	m
g	the vertical term of the Gaussian equation	m
H _e	the emission height of the source	m
h	the height of the mixing layer	m

Since the above algorithm for the dilution factor at the receiving point has been built into the CALPUFF model and is real-time, it is possible to use the emission concentrations at the receiving point calculated by the CALPUFF model and replace the equation for the dilution factor with a simple linear relationship, as shown in Equation (5):

$$C = Q \times f \tag{5}$$

where C is the pollutant concentration at the receiving point (mg/m³); Q is the source intensity of motor vehicle emissions (mg/(veh·m)); and f is the dilution factor.

$$C_{limit} = Q_{limit} \times f \tag{6}$$

The authors obtained the *C_{limit}* value by consulting the secondary limit values of the basic ambient air pollutant concentrations of China national standards (see Table 5) and calculated the *Q_{limit}* value for the upper limit of motor vehicle emissions by using the dilution factor f obtained from CULPUFF by Equation (6), where, *C_{limit}* is the national standard limit value (g/m³), *Q_{limit}* is the emission limit of motor vehicles (g), and *f* is the dilution factor.

The authors calculated the CET (ambient allowable traffic) using Equation (7), knowing the *Q_{limit}* for the total restricted emissions from motor vehicles. If there are multiple pollutant types, the CET should be the smallest of all pollutant types.

$$CET \leq \frac{3600Q_{limit}}{e} \tag{7}$$

where Q_{limit} is the total restricted motor vehicle emissions (g); CET is the environmental allowable traffic volume (pcu·h⁻¹); e is the emission is the emission factor.

2) Calculation of the capacity of environment traffic at the intersection

The authors calculated the maximum hourly concentrations of each pollutant, intersection emission factors, and emission inventory values for all grid points within the intersection for the full time period of the study population, respectively, based on the results of the VISSIM-MOVES-CALPUFF model described above, combined with the ambient allowable traffic volume model established above. The results of the ambient allowable traffic values for the existing intersections are shown in Table 10.

Table 10 Traffic limits for various pollutants

Pollutant	CPOC/g·m ⁻³	Dilution factor	SNSL /g·m ⁻³	Total emission limit/g	CET/pcu·h ⁻¹
CO	1.84E-03	1.26E-07	0.004 00	8.79	15 142
NOX	1.17E-04	1.26E-07	0.000 08	0.18	4 777
PM2.5	5.57E-06	1.28E-07	0.000 15	0.33	188 157
PM10	6.96E-06	1.28E-07	0.000 08	0.16	75 265

[Notes: CPOC (control point output concentration), SNSL (standard national standard limit)]

From Table 10, it can be obtained that the threshold value of the ambient traffic tolerance traffic volume for this intersection section is 4,777 pcu/h, while from the results of the study, it can be seen that the actual traffic volume during the peak hours of traffic flow totals 6,921 pcu/h (the natural number before converting the equivalent number is 6,867 veh/h).

The above results indicate that the current air quality impact of motor vehicle emissions at this intersection is beyond the carrying capacity of the environment. Therefore, it is necessary to adopt policy restrictions or technical improvement measures to effectively prevent the damage to the air environment and the impact on the health of the residents from the operation of the traffic system.

Conclusion

Firstly, at the intersection of Tiyu Street and Peace Road, the diffusion of pollutant emissions CO and NOX from the traffic area is wider than other pollutants, and is significantly influenced by wind direction and speed during diffusion. According to the analysis of weekday intersection emissions, the pollutant emissions at this intersection are positively correlated with the changes in traffic volume. During the morning peak period, the rapid increase in tailpipe emissions due to the surge of motor vehicles during the peak period, and the road pollution generated by a large number of vehicles cannot be dissipated in a short period of time, resulting in a much greater concentration of various indicators in the road environment than in the residential environment. However, in terms of daily average pollutant concentrations, residents breathe more pollutants at fixed locations off the road than on the road. In other words, the pollution caused by traffic is not necessarily less than that caused by road travel during the period when the individual is at a fixed location. This may be due to the height and density of the building structures being higher than the intersection, resulting in a prolonged accumulation of pollutant gases that cannot dissipate in a short period of time due to the poor degree of ventilation after diffusion into the area.

Secondly, the authors developed a capacity of environment traffic (CET) calculation model based on the Green-Shield linear traffic flow model, combined with MOVES emission factors and CALPUFF dilution factors and applied the new model to calculate the ambient allowable traffic volume thresholds of intersections and road sections to assess whether the actual traffic volume exceeds the ambient standard traffic volume limits. The results indicate that the current impact of motor vehicle emissions on air quality at this intersection exceeds the carrying capacity of the environment, and the

traffic emissions put the entire atmospheric environment under certain pressure, which will affect the comprehensive atmospheric quality of the urban area to a certain extent. Therefore, policy restrictions or technical improvement measures are necessary to effectively prevent the damage to the air environment and the impact on the health of residents from the operation of the transportation system.

Finally, based on the findings of this paper, the authors suggest that traffic management departments should reasonably plan the traffic road network according to the land use of various types of urban sites and formulate rules for the passage of different types of vehicles to reduce congested road sections on the one hand and reduce motor vehicle pollutant emissions on the other. Traffic management departments should also consider directing traffic flow to intersection sections away from residential areas to reduce the impact of traffic pollutants on the resident population. For residents of fixed places, they should go out less during peak vehicle periods and avoid the exchange of indoor and outdoor air to reduce the impact of traffic pollutants on human health.

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Appendix A Workday intersection survey traffic (Unit: veh·h-1)

Direction	Drainage direction	Time Slot	S-Bus	M-Bus	L- Bus	S-Vans	M-Vans	L-Vans	Total
East Import	Left turn direction	07:00~08:00	446	1	8	0	0	0	455
		08:00~09:00	412	0	4	0	0	0	416
		10:00~11:00	338	2	6	26	2	0	374
		12:00~13:00	168	0	4	4	1	0	177
		14:00~15:00	284	0	4	28	6	0	322
		16:00~17:00	340	0	2	22	0	0	364
		18:00~19:00	382	0	4	6	0	2	394
	Straight direction	07:00~08:00	64	0	14	4	0	0	82
		08:00~09:00	154	0	28	8	0	0	190
		10:00~11:00	44	4	14	1	1	0	64
		12:00~13:00	24	2	14	11	1	0	52
		14:00~15:00	20	0	12	3	1	0	36
		16:00~17:00	48	2	12	4	0	0	66
	Right turn direction	07:00~08:00	196	4	8	2	0	0	210

		08:00~09:00	192	0	2	6	0	0	200
		10:00~11:00	288	0	0	28	4	2	322
		12:00~13:00	140	1	15	17	2	1	176
		14:00~15:00	250	0	0	27	2	1	280
		16:00~17:00	268	0	0	27	3	0	298
		18:00~19:00	302	0	12	4	0	0	318
West Import	Left turn direction	07:00~08:00	1 112	2	22	6	0	0	1 142
		08:00~09:00	780	6	22	6	0	0	814
		10:00~11:00	828	12	55	46	8	3	952
		12:00~13:00	880	2	14	38	10	4	948
		14:00~15:00	722	4	50	37	7	2	822
		16:00~17:00	1 074	10	70	62	10	4	1 230
	18:00~19:00	1 208	5	43	20	0	0	1 276	
	Straight direction	07:00~08:00	44	0	14	2	0	0	60
		08:00~09:00	26	0	22	2	0	0	50
		10:00~11:00	32	4	14	3	0	1	54
		12:00~13:00	16	3	13	5	2	1	40
		14:00~15:00	18	3	17	3	1	0	42
		16:00~17:00	40	1	15	8	3	0	67
	18:00~19:00	8	2	18	0	0	0	28	
	Right turn direction	07:00~08:00	478	2	14	2	0	0	496
		08:00~09:00	564	3	15	4	0	0	586
		10:00~11:00	402	1	13	3	2	1	422
		12:00~13:00	264	2	10	19	6	3	304
14:00~15:00		344	4	8	6	4	2	368	
16:00~17:00		418	1	9	27	5	2	462	
18:00~19:00	328	3	15	8	0	0	354		
South Import	Left turn direction	07:00~08:00	358	3	19	10	0	0	390
		08:00~09:00	300	2	16	8	0	0	326
		10:00~11:00	434	3	35	0	0	0	472
		12:00~13:00	352	2	14	10	2	0	380
		14:00~15:00	388	0	32	7	1	0	428
		16:00~17:00	374	4	44	8	2	0	432
	18:00~19:00	402	1	27	2	0	0	432	
	Straight direction	07:00~08:00	1 044	6	24	62	0	26	1162
		08:00~09:00	1 016	4	22	58	0	6	1106
		10:00~11:00	1 136	30	20	24	8	8	1226
		12:00~13:00	748	2	18	54	5	1	828
		14:00~15:00	886	16	16	36	18	8	980
		16:00~17:00	1 304	3	17	29	2	1	1356
	18:00~19:00	1 250	3	31	14	0	0	1298	
	Right turn direction	07:00~08:00	274	0	0	2	0	2	278
		08:00~09:00	232	0	0	0	0	0	232
		10:00~11:00	196	0	0	6	0	2	204
		12:00~13:00	120	0	0	10	2	0	132
14:00~15:00		126	0	0	20	0	4	150	
16:00~17:00		174	0	0	14	6	0	194	
18:00~19:00	190	0	0	15	4	0	209		
North Import	Left turn direction	07:00~08:00	186	2	0	6	0	6	200
		08:00~09:00	200	0	0	14	0	0	214
		10:00~11:00	192	0	2	22	4	4	224
		12:00~13:00	176	1	3	20	3	1	204
		14:00~15:00	150	0	0	16	3	1	170
		16:00~17:00	156	2	6	13	2	1	180
		18:00~19:00	214	0	2	6	0	0	222

Straight direction	07:00~08:00	1 560	0	12	56	2	14	1 644	
	08:00~09:00	1 576	6	32	62	0	2	1 678	
	10:00~11:00	1 112	0	12	82	2	2	1 210	
	12:00~13:00	872	2	18	70	5	1	968	
	14:00~15:00	938	3	13	62	8	0	1 024	
	16:00~17:00	1 120	0	28	28	2	0	1 178	
	18:00~19:00	1 164	0	16	8	0	0	1 188	
	Right turn direction	07:00~08:00	696	0	4	46	0	2	748
		08:00~09:00	762	2	2	32	2	0	800
		10:00~11:00	562	2	6	66	12	4	652
		12:00~13:00	512	0	2	60	10	4	588
		14:00~15:00	682	0	2	78	8	0	770
		16:00~17:00	616	0	2	62	22	0	702
		18:00~19:00	628	2	12	30	0	2	674

[Notes: S-Bus (small bus), M-Bus (medium bus), L- Bus (lager bus), S-Vans (small vans), M-Van (medium vans), L-Van (large vans)]

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